

DIGITAL SOCIAL CAPITAL ON CAREER SUCCESS IN DIGITAL NATIVES AND DIGITAL IMMIGRANT EMPLOYEES

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to explore the implications of the industrial revolution 4.0 on the development of the concept of social capital (digital social capital) on employee career success in Indonesia. This study uses a quantitative approach. The research hypothesis was tested using Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with multi-group analysis (MGA) using Smart-PLS 4. The sample was 215 respondents (101 digital native groups and 114 digital immigrant groups) in Indonesia. The research results found that digital social trust had a positive effect on the career success of digital natives and digital immigrants. Digital social cliques have a positive effect on the career success of digital natives. However, digital social cliques do not affect the career success of digital immigrants. Digital social networking does not affect the career success of digital natives and digital immigrants. Digital social obligation does not affect the career success of digital natives. However, digital social obligation has a positive effect on the career success of digital immigrants. Career success can be studied with a broader interpretation based on digital social trust, digital social cliques, digital social networks and digital social obligations.

Keywords: *Digital social capital, Digital natives, Digital immigrant, Career success, Indonesia*

1. INTRODUCTION

Individuals who have social capital compared to others who do not, they hold more favorable positions in networks, giving them access to a range of individuals with the knowledge needed to contribute to the smooth operation of the company and, consequently, more favorable career outcomes, like quicker promotions [1] and career success [2].

There has been a conceptual shift in the idea of social capital. Social cliques [3], reciprocity norms [4], trust [5], and mentoring networks [6] were the initial understandings of the concept of social capital. Additionally, Kistyanto [7] integrated the concept of social capital from four theoretical approaches (trust, social cliques, social networks, and social obligations). Whereas, Seibert et al. [2] integrated the concept of social capital from three different theoretical approaches (weak-tie theory, structural hole theory, and social resource theory).

The company's ability to leverage its social capital has led to many incredible discoveries.

The use of new technology in a variety of fields, including biotechnology, the internet of things, robotics, block chains, nanotechnology, quantum computers, artificial intelligence, 3D printers, and unmanned vehicles, is currently characterized by the 4.0 industry revolution [8]. Manufacturing, logistics, and other industrial processes have integrated the cyberphysical system, the internet of things, and services from the fourth industrial revolution [8]. In exchange, the industrial revolution 4.0 gave rise to digital social capital, which includes digital social trust, digital social cliques, digital social networks, and digital social obligations [7]. Digital social capital is a new perspective in the development of the concept of social capital.

The term “social capital” in an organization refers to the traits of a social organization, including information, trust, and reciprocity norms [9]. One way to think of social trust is as a by product of social relationships [7]. According to Fukuyama [5], organizations and groups with the highest levels of social capital or trust are the most successful. An attitude or feeling known as “digital

social trust” is said to be produced through frequent social interactions between subordinates and superiors within the organization. The best explanation for career success is that attitudes and feelings matter more than knowledge acquisition and recall [9].

According to Granovetter [3] weak ties theory, members of a social clique typically have strong ties (affiliations); emotions within the group are often intense, involve multiple relationships, such as friends, advisors, and co-workers, and occur frequently. Members of this social clique are likely to share information with other members quickly. On the other hand, relationships with people outside of the social clique are typically weak because they are restricted to a single kind of relationship, do not happen often, and are not very intense emotionally. According to Kistyanto [10] research, career success is significantly impacted by social cliques.

According to Friedman & Krackhardt [11], social capital is derived from interpersonal relationships and grows when an individual's position within a social network is considered a valuable resource. According to Florin et al. [12], networks offer value to their members through the social resources that are integrated within the network. The degree to which people can find profitable networks in which they are linked to people who have the resources—like information and money—needed to attain favorable results in their professional and work lives indicates how much social capital they possess. According to Adler & Kwon [13], social capital cannot exist without networks since they offer chances to connect and engage with others.

Social ties have a positive effect on career success [10]. This means that managers think that social relationships must be based on mutually beneficial principles such as social ties, such as the obligation to repay services to other people who have helped as an expression of gratitude. This fact is in accordance with Bourdieu's theory [14] which states that in social relationships such as friendship, there is a mandate called “credit” that must be paid back as compensation (debt).

This research aims to explore the implications of the industrial revolution 4.0 on the development of the concept of social capital (digital social capital) and empirically test its influence on employee career success. This research will try to identify and compare the career success of an employee who is currently working for a company in Indonesia in two different groups,

namely the digital natives group and the digital immigrant group in Indonesia.

2. LITERATUE REVIEW

Digital natives and digital immigrants

Those who were raised in an era where digital technology was both already in use and just beginning to advance are known as digital natives [15]. They often feel comfortable and adept at using digital technology and social media to communicate, collaborate, and learn. According to Lawter & Garnjost [16], digital natives have been exposed to digital technology from a young age and often rely on it for daily activities such as communication, entertainment and learning. They tend to have a high level of digital literacy and are able to quickly adapt to new technologies and digital platforms. Digital immigrants are individuals who have to adapt to digital technology later in life, often as adults [15]. They have experienced significant changes in the way they live and work due to the proliferation of digital technology, and may not be as comfortable or adept at using it as digital natives. Digital immigrants may require more formal training and instruction to use them effectively.

According to Hakkarainen et al. [17], the appropriate age range or criteria for classifying someone as a digital native or immigrant is not well defined, but generally refers to individuals born before or after the proliferation of digital technology in everyday life. Some researchers have used age ranges such as in Prensky [18] research, those born between 1980 and now are digital natives, while those born before 1980 are considered digital immigrants.

Digital social capital

Digital social capital refers to social networks, relationships, and norms of trust and reciprocity that are created and maintained through digital platforms such as social media, online communities, and other digital tools [19]. A person or organization's actual and potential resources in digital social trust, digital social cliques, digital social networking, and digital social obligations are collectively referred to as their digital social capital [20]. It includes the same principles as traditional social capital, but is built and maintained through digital interactions and relationships. Digital social capital can take many forms, including online friendships, followers, likes, shares, comments, and reviews [21]. It may also include access to information and resources through digital networks, such as

recommendations for products or services, job opportunities, or other types of support. Digital social capital is becoming increasingly important in today's interconnected world, as more and more people rely on digital platforms for communication, networking and social interaction. However, like traditional social capital, digital social capital can also be exclusionary and reinforce inequalities, especially if based on factors such as digital literacy, access to technology, or social status.

In this study, the digital social capital variable is divided into four dimensions, namely digital social trust, digital social cliques, digital social networking, and digital social obligation. Digital social trust is the level of trust that individuals have in the security and reliability of technology, platforms and digital services [22]. Digital social trust is important because it underlies many aspects of our modern lives, from online shopping and banking to social media and digital communications.

Digital social cliques refer to groups of people who form and interact with each other online based on the same interests, beliefs, or social identities where fellow group members have a high level of esprit de corps. These groups can form on various digital platforms, such as social media, online forums, or messaging apps, and can include people from all over the world who may have never met in person.

Digital social networking refers to the use of online platforms and tools to connect and communicate with others that allow individuals to connect with friends, family, and colleagues regardless of geographic location [23].

Digital social obligations are norms of reciprocity in the digital world that describe the level of context in social systems, where individuals provide services to other individuals by donating something but with the general hope that this kindness will be reciprocated in the future [20]. Because digital technology and online platforms continue to shape our lives, there is an increasing need for individuals and organizations to consider the impact of their actions on others in the digital space.

3. HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Digital social trust and career success

Digital social trust is the honesty possessed by someone that makes them worthy of trust in the digital world. Behaving consistently, being responsible/trustworthy, respecting/respected each other, and being sincere are some of the

domains of a person's digital social trust in the digital world [20]. Fukuyama [5] stated that the core of social capital is trust. Because trust will underlie and strengthen other parameters. Without trust, other parameters cannot be implemented properly. To be able to work together, help each other, build partnerships, spread norms, and be committed, mutual trust is needed. Based on this, the present study proposes the following hypotheses.

H1. Digital social trust will be positively related to career success

Digital social cliques and career success

Digital social cliques are online social groups made up of friends, coworkers, and other acquaintances. They are characterized by strong, intense, interactive, and mutually supportive emotional bonds between their members [20]. According to Granovetter [3] weak ties theory, members of a social clique typically have strong ties (affiliations); emotions within the group are often intense, involve multiple relationships, such as friends, advisors, and coworkers, and occur frequently. Members of this social clique are likely to share information with other members quickly. On the other hand, relationships with people outside of the social clique are typically weak because they are restricted to a single kind of relationship, do not happen often, and are not very intense emotionally. According to Kistiyanto [10] research, career success is significantly impacted by social cliques. Thus, the following is how the study's hypotheses are put forth.

H2. Digital social cliques will be positively related to career success

Digital social networking and career success

Digital social networking is a type of social connection created in the digital sphere that consists of people and organizations connected to each other and bound by one or more specific relationship types. Similar to a person's membership in a social media site like Facebook, Twitter, Friendster, Myspace, LinkedIn, Google+, WAG, etc., is this digital social network. Participating in this virtual social network enables an individual to communicate with peers, supervisors, subordinates, and the general public from a range of positions and professions [20]. By building a strong digital social network, a person can gain access to valuable resources, information, and opportunities that can help them achieve their

career goals. For example, an individual with a strong digital social network may have access to job openings that are not publicly advertised, be introduced to potential mentors or sponsors who can provide guidance and support, and gain insight into industry trends and best practices. Additionally, having a strong digital social network can help individuals stay up to date with the latest technology and trends in their field, which is important for remaining competitive in today's fast-paced digital environment. Based on this, the present study proposes the following hypotheses.

- H3. Digital social networking will be positively related to career success

Digital social obligation and career success

The concept of digital social obligation pertains to the reciprocity norm in the digital realm. It characterizes the degree of agreement within a social structure where people offer assistance to one another at a cost, generally expecting a return favor in the future [20]. Career success is positively impacted by social ties [10]. This indicates that managers believe social relationships should be built on mutually beneficial ideas like social ties, such as the need to return favors or show gratitude to those who have assisted. This information is consistent with Bourdieu's theory [14], which holds that there is a requirement known as "credit" that must be repaid as compensation in social relationships like friendship (debt of gratitude). Thus, the following is how the study's hypotheses are put forth.

- H4. Digital social obligation will be positively related to career success

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of this research. A total of 4 dimensions act as independent variables (digital social capital) while the career success variable is the dependent variable.

4. METHODS

Design and participants

Considering the nature of the research problem, a quantitative approach is used in this study. This study employs judgment sampling, a sort of purposive sampling, as a non-probability sampling technique. Employees in Indonesia who fall into the categories of digital immigrants and natives make up the research population. There were 215 samples in this study, with 101 respondents belonging to the group of digital natives and 114 respondents to the group of digital immigrants.

Respondents' profile

The minimal need for the sample size question is five times the number of variables to be evaluated in the observations [[24] [25]]. A total of 266 online surveys were sent out, of which 215 were returned. These results served as the foundation for further study. According to Hair et al. [24], 200 samples should be used to give reliable estimations. Because of this, the study's sample size ($n = 215$) is deemed sufficient for testing the suggested hypothesis using Structural Equation Model - Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS).

Using a frequency test, six demographic components in total were presented. The six demographic profiles include: gender, age, last educational attainment, organizational position, total work experience, gross monthly income, degree of gadget use, and amount of promotion. Based on gender, the majority of respondents were male with 151 respondents (70.2%). Based on age, the majority of respondents were >40 years old (53%). Based on the latest education, the majority of respondents had a D4/S1 education, 129 people (60%). Based on position in the organization, the majority of respondents were in staff/employee positions, 53 people (24.7%). Based on total years of work experience, the majority of respondents have experience of >20 years (33%). Based on gross monthly income, the majority of respondents earned IDR 5.000.001 - IDR 10.000.000 (25.7%). Based on the intensity of using gadgets, the majority of respondents last 5 – 8 hours (41%). Based on the number of promotions, the majority of respondents received promotions 1 – 5 times (73%).

Measures and data analysis

In this study, a total of 39 statement items were submitted. Digital social trust was measured with an 8-item adapted from Chen [9]. Furthermore, this study measures digital social cliques using a 9-item online identity bubble reinforcement scale (IBRIS)

[[26][27]]; and a 1-item developed directly by researchers to measure respondents' self-reported involvement in click online on social media. To measure digital social networks, adapted 4-item from Chen [9]. Respondents were asked if they agree that they have connections in public relations, advertising, journalism, and communication education. This research uses a 5-item created directly by researchers to measure digital social obligations.

Gattiker & Larwood [28] multidimensional career success measure was adopted in this research, namely financial success (3-items) and hierarchical success (4-items); as well as 5-item career satisfaction from Greenhaus et al. [29]. All items are rated on a 5-point Likert scale, with respondents indicating whether they agree or disagree with each statement (1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree).

The data was analyzed using the SEM-PLS, which was aided by the computer program Smart-PLS 4. The SPSS 23 was used for the variables' descriptive analysis and demographic statistical analysis of the respondent characteristics. Comparison of the same model between two groups of respondents, namely the digital native group and the digital immigrant group in Indonesia, was analyzed using Multi Group Analysis (MGA). PLS-SEM has a high degree of statistical power compared to CB-SEM. This indicates that PLS-SEM has a higher probability of identifying relationships that are as significant as the population as a whole. Because it is consistent with recent research published in credible journals, the authors of this study have chosen to use PLS-SEM [25]. A measurement model and a structural model were the two processes that Smart PLS was used for [30].

5. RESULT

Measurement model assessment

Using Smart PLS 4, we first ran the measurement model to make sure the constructs were correctly correlated with the suggested variance. Therefore, in order to evaluate the measurement model in this study, convergent and discriminant validity were examined. In the first step, the factor loadings of every item were examined in order to assess the convergent validity. Loadings ought to be at least 0.50, according to Rahman et al. [30]. In particular, every item in Table 1 had an outer loading greater than 0.50. An internal consistency check was performed on this study using composite reliability (CR). For CR, Hair et al. [24] recommended a cutoff value of 0.70. The study's total item CR

ranged from 0.914 to 0.935, surpassing the suggested threshold of 0.7. Next, the reliability test results from the CR results can be strengthened by cronbach's alpha (CA). Alternatively, the usefulness of CA in assessing internal consistency could be stated.

In this study, the CA was greater than 0.70 and varied from 0.877 to 0.920. Ultimately, the study's convergent validity was verified by examining average variance extracted (AVE). Hair et al. [24] state that AVE stands for the grand mean value of the squared loadings of the study's construct-related indicators. According to Hair et al. [24], an AVE value of 0.50 indicates that 50% of the items provide adequate explanation about the construct. All of the constructs in this study had AVE values that fell outside of the suggested range of 0.507 to 0.727. The convergent validity of each confirmed construct in this study is displayed in Table 1.

Table 1. Specified Measurement Model

Variabel	Loading	CA	CR	AVE
Digital Social Capital (X)				
<i>Digital Social Trust (X1)</i>		0.920	0.935	0.642
Based on digital reputation, when I encounter a problem, there will be many colleagues in my partner organization that I can ask for advice	0.750			
Based on digital reputation, when I encounter problems, my colleagues can be trusted	0.698			
Based on digital reputation, when I encounter problems, my organization will provide assistance	0.807			
Based on digital reputation, when I encounter problems, my superiors will provide assistance	0.825			
Based on digital reputation, when I encounter problems, my colleagues will provide professional advice	0.856			
Based on digital reputation, when I encounter	0.856			

problems, my colleagues will take the time to help				
Based on digital reputation, when I encounter problems, my colleagues will encourage me	0.836			
Based on digital reputation, my colleagues will help me complete my work	0.770			
<i>Digital Social Cliques (X2)</i>		0.908	0.923	0.547
On social media, I join a society or community which is an important part of my identity	0.788			
On social media, I belong to a society or community that I am proud of	0.851			
On social media, I become part of a society or community that I can join	0.783			
On social media, I prefer to interact with people who are like me	0.720			
On social media, I prefer to interact with people who have the same interests as me	0.677			
On social media, I prefer to interact with people who share my values	0.691			
On social media, I trust the information shared with me	0.630			
On social media, I feel like people think like me	0.646			
On social media, I can keep myself well informed	0.772			
On social media, I have a high esprit de corps	0.805			
<i>Digital Social Networking (X3)</i>		0.877	0.914	0.727
I have digital connections in the news industry	0.793			
I have digital connections in advertising	0.831			
I have digital connections in public relations	0.890			
I have a digital connection in	0.892			

communication education				
<i>Digital Social Obligation (X4)</i>		0.903	0.928	0.722
I feel I have an obligation to share my experiences on social media with those who have shared their experiences with me	0.895			
I feel I have an obligation to share knowledge on social media with those who have shared knowledge with me	0.903			
I feel I have an obligation to share gifts on social media with those who have shared gifts with me	0.786			
I feel I have an obligation to share my skills on social media with those who have shared my skills with me	0.844			
I feel I have an obligation to share recommendations on social media with parties who have shared recommendations with me	0.815			
Career Success (Y)		0.916	0.924	0.507
I receive fair compensation compared to my peers	0.745			
I expect to earn a high income compared to my colleagues	0.528			
I earn as much as I think my job is worth	0.743			
I am happy with the promotions I have received so far	0.783			
I will achieve my career goals within the time frame I set for myself	0.764			
I will achieve all my career goals	0.782			
My current job offers adequate opportunities for promotion	0.800			
I am satisfied with the success I have	0.660			

achieved in my career				
I am satisfied with the progress I have made towards meeting my overall career goals	0.670			
I am satisfied with the progress I have made towards meeting my income goals	0.607			
I am satisfied with the progress I am making towards achieving my goals for progress	0.706			
I am satisfied with the progress I am making towards meeting my goals for the development of new skills	0.710			

The measurement model's discriminant validity was used after its convergent validity. The square root of AVE was compared to the correlation of the other constructs in order to assess the discriminant validity. The results of the study showed that the square root of AVE is higher than the correlation value of the other constructs. Given that the constructs shared a greater amount of variance with their associated indicator than any other construct, the Fornell-Larcker criterion verified the measurement model's discriminant validity. According to the Fornell-Larcker criteria [30]. Table 2 displays the statistics for discriminant validity.

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

Variabel	Mean	CS	DSC	DSN	DSO	DST
CS	3.66	0.712				
DSC	3.44	0.532	0.740			
DSN	3.18	0.292	0.459	0.853		
DSO	3.33	0.354	0.477	0.215	0.850	
DST	3.77	0.545	0.527	0.282	0.204	0.801

We then used the three-box method of interpretation based on the responses provided by the respondents. The range of five must be divided by three to produce a range of 1.33 (1.00 - 2.33 = low; 2.34 - 3.67 = moderate; 3.68 - 5.00 = high) based on the likert-scale answer selection criteria. This range is then used as the foundation for the interpretation of the variable's average value [30]. According to the respondents' evaluations of the research variables (DST = 3.77; DSC = 3.44; DSN = 3.18; DSO = 3.33 dan CS = 3.66), one latent

variable is classified as a high category and four as a moderate category.

Structural model assessment

To assess the significance of the hypotheses, it has been suggested that the path coefficients, p-values, and t-statistics in the structural model be reported [24]. evaluating the structural model by examining the significant value in order to ascertain the relationship between the variables using the bootstrapping method. The outcomes of the research model relationships' hypothesis testing are displayed in Table 3.

Table 3. Hypothesis Testing

Relationship	Coefficient	t-value	p-value	Decision
Model Data Digital Natives				
Digital social trust → career success	0.353	3.654	0.000	Accepted
Digital social cliques → career success	0.262	1.997	0.046	Accepted
Digital social networking → career success	0.099	0.887	0.376	Rejected
Digital social obligation → career success	0.154	0.991	0.322	Rejected
Model Data Digital Immigrants				
Digital social trust → career success	0.387	3.410	0.001	Accepted
Digital social cliques → career success	0.219	1.712	0.087	Rejected
Digital social networking → career success	0.004	0.051	0.959	Rejected
Digital social obligation → career success	0.202	1.976	0.049	Accepted
Model Data Multi Group Analysis				
Digital social trust → career success	0.374	5.327	0.000	Accepted
Digital social cliques → career success	0.242	2.824	0.005	Accepted
Digital social networking → career success	0.043	0.702	0.483	Rejected
Digital social obligation → career success	0.153	2.049	0.041	Accepted

In the previous H1 discussion, digital social trust will be positively related to career success. The results of path analysis show that this relationship is significant both in the data models of digital natives ($\beta = 0.353$, t-statistics = 3.654, p-value 0.000), digital immigrants ($\beta = 0.387$, t-statistics = 3.410, p-value 0.001), and multi group analysis ($\beta = 0.374$, t-statistics = 5.327, p-value 0.000), so that H1 is accepted.

Furthermore, the results confirm the acceptance of the H2, which shows that the

relationship between digital social cliques has a positive and significant effect on career success ($\beta = 0.262$, t-statistics = 1.997, p-value = 0.046) data models of digital natives and multi group analysis ($\beta = 0.242$, t-statistics = 2.824, p-value = 0.005). However, this result has no effect in data model of digital immigrants ($\beta = 0.219$, t-statistics = 1.712, p-value = 0.087), so H2 is rejected.

In the previous H3 discussion, digital social networking will be positively related to career success. The results of path analysis show that this relationship is not significant both in the data models of digital natives ($\beta = 0.099$, t-statistics = 0.887, p-value 0.376), digital immigrants ($\beta = 0.004$, t-statistics = 0.051, p-value 0.959), and multi group analysis ($\beta = 0.043$, t-statistics = 0.702, p-value 0.483), so that H3 is rejected.

Likewise, H4, because the results show that digital social obligation positively and significantly affects career success ($\beta = 0.202$, t-statistics = 1.976, p-value = 0.049) data models of digital immigrants and ($\beta = 0.153$, t-statistics = 2.049, p-value = 0.041) multi group analysis, this hypothesis is accepted. However, this result has no effect in data model of digital natives ($\beta = 0.154$, t-statistics = 0.991, p-value = 0.322), so H4 is rejected.

6. DISCUSSION

The industrial revolution 4.0 has implications for the development of human capital and social capital theories. Flores & Lu [31] propose a new approach and term with a human-focused perspective to address the challenges of the future workforce. This new term is "Human Capital 4.0". Individuals with more investment in their human resources can develop professional skills, increase productivity in the workplace, and then get positive rewards from the organization [32]. Human capital and social capital are interrelated Coleman [4] and are positively related to organizational success [[11][33]].

Based on the results of statistical analysis, it is known that digital social trust has a positive effect on the career success of digital native respondents in Indonesia. Apart from that, it can also be seen that digital social trust has a positive effect on the career success of digital immigrant respondents in Indonesia.

The term "social capital" in an organization refers to the traits of a social organization, including knowledge, trust, and reciprocity norms [9]. One way to think of social trust is as a byproduct of social relationships [34]. According

to Fukuyama [5], organizations and groups with the highest levels of social capital or trust are the most successful. An attitude or feeling known as "digital social trust" is said to be produced through frequent social interactions between subordinates and superiors within the organization. The best explanation for career success is that attitudes and feelings matter more than knowledge acquisition and recall [9].

Digital social cliques are known to positively impact the career success of digital native respondents in Indonesia, as indicated by statistical analysis results. Researchers in the social psychology research tradition have studied group formation behavior in great detail over the past century. People prioritize their own groups in addition to forming them very quickly, even in small groups [26]. On social media, people often make fast decisions in content evaluation and communication, and they tend to rely on their friends' evaluations and opinions [[35][36][37]]. Thus, group memberships and online social networks have an impact on which content people trust and encounter on social media [38]. Kistyanto [10] research shows that social clicks have a significant effect on career success. However, it can be seen that digital social cliques have no effect on the career success of digital immigrant respondents in Indonesia. Based on the results of descriptive statistical analysis for each variable, the digital social cliques variable is in the medium category. Apart from that, the career success variable is also in the medium category.

If we look at the value of the digital social cliques variable statement item, there are only two items (on social media, I am part of a society or community that I can join; and on social media, I can keep myself well informed) out of ten items statements that are in the high category. The eight items in the medium category are: on social media, I am part of a society or community which is an important part of my identity; on social media, I belong to a society or community that I am proud of; on social media, I prefer to interact with people who are like me; on social media, I prefer to interact with people who have the same interests as me; on social media, I prefer to interact with people who share my values; on social media, I trust the information shared with me; on social media, I feel like people think like me; as well as on social media, I have a high esprit de corps. Based on these results, it can be concluded that respondents in the digital immigrant group in Indonesia have not fully formed and interacted with each other online based on the same interests, beliefs or social identities

where fellow group members have a high esprit de corps.

Based on the results of statistical analysis, it is known that digital social networking has no effect on the career success of digital native respondents in Indonesia. Apart from that, it can also be seen that digital social networking has no effect on the career success of digital immigrant respondents in Indonesia. If viewed from the results of the descriptive statistical analysis of each variable, the digital social networking variable is in the medium category. Apart from that, the career success variable is also in the medium category.

If viewed from the value of the digital social networking variable statement items, the four statement items are in the medium category. These items are: I have digital connections in the news industry; I have digital connections in advertising; I have digital connections in public relations; and I have digital connections in communication education. Based on these results, it can be concluded that respondents in the digital natives and digital immigrants group in Indonesia have not yet fully built a strong digital social network, so that a person can gain access to valuable resources, information and opportunities that can help them achieve their career goals.

Social trust can account for a substantial portion of the variance in career success, even though social networks, one aspect of social capital, do not predict career success. These results can be interpreted in one of two ways: either social networks show differences in accessibility to different information sources, or they represent functional ties between individuals. This is in line with the characteristics of digital immigrant respondents who prefer to interact face-to-face, not via social media [39]. On the other hand, social trust is defined as a mindset or feeling that results from intense interpersonal interactions between superiors and subordinates within the organization. The best explanation for career success is that attitudes and feelings matter more than knowledge acquisition and recall [9].

Based on the results of statistical analysis, it is known that digital social obligation has no effect on the career success of digital native respondents in Indonesia. If viewed from the results of the descriptive statistical analysis of each variable, the digital social obligation variable is in the medium category. Apart from that, the career success variable is also in the medium category.

If viewed from the value of the digital social obligation variable statement items, the five statement items are in the medium category. These

items are: I feel I have an obligation to share experiences on social media with parties who have shared experiences with me; I feel I have an obligation to share knowledge on social media with those who have shared knowledge with me; I feel I have an obligation to share gifts on social media with those who have shared gifts with me; I feel I have an obligation to share my skills on social media with those who have shared my skills with me; and I feel I have an obligation to share recommendations on social media with parties who have shared recommendations with me.

These findings lead to the conclusion that respondents in the Indonesian group of digital natives have not fully adopted the norm of reciprocity in the digital world, which characterizes the degree of agreement in a social system where people help others at the expense of something in the general expectation that they will be helped in return in the future [20].

Nonetheless, it is evident that respondents who are digital immigrants in Indonesia have better career success when they fulfill their digital social obligation. Career success is positively impacted by social ties [10]. This indicates that managers believe social relationships should be built on mutually beneficial ideas like social ties, such as the need to return favors or show gratitude to those who have assisted. This fact is consistent with Bourdieu's [14] theory, which holds that there is a mandate called "credit" in social relationships, like friendships, that needs to be paid back as compensation (debt of gratitude).

Limitations and future directions

To confirm the cross-sectional study effects of digital social capital on career success in management, more research utilizing longitudinal [[40][41]] designs will be required. By incorporating multiple mediators (like perceived employability and innovative behavior [42]) and/or moderators (like organizational career management practices and team power distance [43]) in the research model, future studies may concentrate on the when and how questions. Qualitative research may also contribute to our understanding of how their professional success has been facilitated by digital social capital. Consequently, qualitative research can offer more detailed insights into the reasons behind the rise in career success associated with digital social capital. Ultimately, a more comprehensive approach to the study of career success is possible.

7. CONCLUSION

Career success can be studied with a broader interpretation based on digital social trust, digital social cliques, digital social networks, and digital social obligations. The research results found that digital social trust had a positive effect on the career success of digital natives and digital immigrants. Digital social cliques have a positive effect on the career success of digital natives. However, digital social cliques do not affect the career success of digital immigrants. Digital social networking does not affect the career success of digital natives and digital immigrants. Digital social obligation does not affect the career success of digital natives. However, digital social obligation has a positive effect on the career success of digital immigrants.

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